

1 **Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: KRT18.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe discovery of Keratin 18 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in human embryonic
11 stem cells.

12 Citations

13 1. Liang, X., Qiu, X., Ma, Y., Xu, W., Chen, S., Zhang, P., Liu, M. and Lin, X., 2023. KRT18 regulates
14 trophoblast cell migration and invasion which are essential for embryo implantation. *Reproductive Biology
15 and Endocrinology*, 21(1), p.78.